

An Analogue of the Acclimatisation Phenomenon in the Protection of Arsenious Sulphide Sol by Gelatine.

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In connection with a study of the coagulation of colloids in the presence of protective agents, to be communicated shortly, the interesting question has arisen about the difference in the stability of a sol produced by a variation in the manner of addition of the protective agent. Since no information on this point is to be found in the literature, it is intended in this note to record results of some preliminary observations which served to indicate this possibility.

Ten c.c. of a stock solution of arsenious sulphide sol were taken in two similar flasks. An equal volume of a 0.05% gelatine solution was added to each. In one set of observations the gelatine was introduced by a single addition and the resulting mixture shaken, whilst in the other, the same volume from the same gelatine solution was added in about twenty instalments, the mixture being shaken similarly after each addition; the two sets of mixtures were then allowed to stand for about 24 hrs. and then equi-coagulating concentrations of a dilute barium chloride solution were determined with the sols. This quantity as a result of ten independent observations on each system was found to be $N/40$ and $N/50$, corresponding to protection by single addition and dropwise addition respectively.

This conclusion was further tested by colorimetric observations. The two limbs of the colorimeter were filled with samples of the two sols and the heights adjusted to equal visibility. One typical set of results is given below:

		Height in mm.	
Single addition	... 10	20	25
Drop-wise addition	... 9	18	22

These results show that greater coagulation (as evidenced by like opacity) is produced in sols protected by drop-wise addition of the gelatine solution. These sols are therefore less stable than those in which the protector solution was added at once. This deduction

is in agreement with the other set of experiments which indicate that the drop-wise addition of the protector corresponds to a lower concentration of the electrolyte solution for producing in the same degree of coagulation. This lower stability of the system might be explained by the following considerations.

It is evident that protection depends upon the adsorption of the protecting agent by the sol. When the introduction of a given amount of the protecting agent is spread over a number of instalments, the resultant of a certain adsorption of the protector by the sol particle might serve as the basis for further adsorption in a subsequent addition and so on. The result is that the net adsorption in the above case, reckoned per colloid particle, is greater than that corresponding to a single addition of the protector. The average size of the particle in the former case would therefore be greater than in the latter and hence the observed difference in coagulability.

Furthermore, it is known that the stability of a particle in a sol is greater, the less the interfacial tension between itself and the immediately contiguous medium. The reduction in this interfacial tension would increase by increasing the concentration of a substance like gelatine, which is an efficient emulsifying agent. This might be another factor in the greater stability of the sol protected by introducing the gelatine solution in a single addition, since the corresponding continuous medium would be richer in gelatine.

It might further be pointed out that there is considerable evidence (Smoluchowski, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1917, 92, 155; Freundlich and Basu, *ibid.*, 1925, 115, 203) to show that stirring, etc., increase the rate of coagulation, presumably by increasing the frequency of collision (leading to coalescence) amongst the colloid particles. Since in drop-wise addition the system is subjected to a longer (intermittent) period of stirring than in the other case, difference in stability as observed is to be anticipated.

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